

GAMMA GLUTAMYL TRANSFERASE AND LACTATE DEHYDROGENASE AS BIOCHEMICAL MARKERS OF SEVERITY OF PREECLAMPSIA

Authors : Shobha M. Munde M.Sc1., N. R. Hazari PhD2*, A. P. Thorat M.D2., S.B.Gaikwad Ph.D2, Veena hatolkar Ph.D3

Abstract : ABSTRACT This study was conducted to examine the possible role of serum Gamma-glutamyltransferase (GGT) and Lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) in the prediction of severity of preeclampsia. The study group comprised of 40 preeclamptic cases (22 with mild and 18 with severe) and 40 healthy normotensive pregnant controls. Serum samples of all the cases were assayed for GGT and LDH. Demographic, hemodynamic and laboratory data as well as serum GGT and LDH levels were compared among the three groups. The results indicated that severe preeclamptic cases had significantly increased levels of serum GGT and LDH. The symptoms in severe preeclamptic women were significantly increased in patients with GGT > 70 IU/L and LDH >800 IU/L. Elevated levels of serum GGT and LDH can be used as biochemical markers which reflects the severity of preeclampsia and useful for the management of preeclampsia to decrease maternal and fetal morbidity and mortality.

Keywords : KEY WORDS: Severe Preeclampsia, GGT, LDH,

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